

Nitromethane as a Polar Solvent: Part IV Solvolytic and Metathetical Reactions

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Antimony (V), titanium (IV), tin (IV), tellurium (IV), zirconium (IV), aluminium (III), iron (III), and arsenic (III) chlorides have been solvolysed in nitromethane. Sodamide and various metal hydrides have also been solvolysed and solvolysed products have been isolated. A few metathetical reactions have also been carried out. These reactions have been explained on the basis of the autoionization of nitromethane as

In continuation of studies in nitromethane as a polar solvent¹⁻³, solvolytic and metathetical reactions have been carried out and are reported here. In various solvents, solvolytic reactions have already been carried out to establish the existence of certain ions formed as a result of their autoionization. In acetyl chloride⁴ and benzoyl chloride⁵ solvolytic reactions have been reported which indicate the existence of chloride (Cl^-) ions as a product of their autoionization. Similar studies have also been reported in ethyl acetate⁶.

Solvolytic reactions in nitromethane are reported here and support the autoionization of the solvent as:

Aluminium chloride is soluble in nitromethane and forms a monosolvate ($\text{AlCl}_3 \cdot \text{CH}_2\text{NO}_2$, m.p. 75-81°). However, on refluxing aluminium chloride with nitromethane hydrochloric acid gas is evolved, resulting in the separation of a yellow solid of the composition $\text{AlCl}(\text{CH}_2\text{NO}_2)_2 \cdot \text{CH}_2\text{NO}_2$. The compound is quite stable (m.p. above 225°C). The mechanism of solvolytic reaction can be represented as follows:

Aluminium in this monosolvate is probably tetra co-ordinated and on heating hydrochloric acid is evolved.

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It has already been pointed out¹⁻³ that one of the hydrogen atoms of methyl group is labile and formation of sodium nitromethane (NaCH_2NO_2) is well known². Due to electron withdrawal by Lewis acid from $\text{N}=\text{O}$ bond in the solvate, the lability of a hydrogen atom of methyl group is enhanced and this helps in the elimination of hydrochloric acid gas. The replacement of a second chlorine atom results in the formation of the compound B which further reacts with another molecule of the solvent

to form a stable solvate which has been isolated. The two possible structures for the compound depending upon sp^3 and sp^3d^2 hybridization of aluminium, are

Since the product is insoluble in usual organic solvents and has a high melting point there is a possibility of the existence of structure II which is dimeric. However the size of nitromethane and its anion may cause steric hindrance in hexa coordination.

Antimony(V) chloride reacts with the solvent to yield a mono-solvate⁴ but on refluxing its dilute solution a yellowish brown solid is formed ($\text{SbCl}_5 \cdot 2\text{CH}_2\text{NO}_2 \cdot \text{CH}_2\text{NO}_2$, m.p. above 200°) and hydrochloric acid gas is evolved. This indicates that out of five

only two chlorine atoms have been replaced by nitromethane ion (CH_2NO_2^-). The product has acquired hexa covalency by attaining sp^3d^2 hybridization by taking up additional molecule of CH_2NO_2 .

Antimony (V) chloride is a quite stable compound and forms a stable solvate with nitromethane. The solvolytic reaction can be easily explained if the solvate is visualized to ionize to liberate a proton or to have a labile hydrogen atom. The possible course of the reaction may be as follows:

Tetra chlorides of tin, zirconium and titanium on refluxing with nitromethane result in the formation of $\text{SnCl}_4 \cdot \text{CH}_2\text{NO}_2 \cdot 2\text{CH}_2\text{NO}_2$; $\text{ZrCl}_4(\text{CH}_2\text{NO}_2)_2 \cdot 2\text{CH}_2\text{NO}_2$ and $\text{TiCl}_4(\text{CH}_2\text{NO}_2)_2 \cdot 2\text{CH}_2\text{NO}_2$ which are brown solids. All these Lewis acids have a tendency to increase their co-ordination number from four to six by acquiring sp^3d^2 or d^2sp^3 hybridization and attaining a stabler octahedral structure. The reactions may be represented as follows:

where M = SnTi or Zr

(II)

However in the case of tin(IV) chloride the reaction stops at stage I. Solvolysis of tellurium (IV) chloride results in the formation of $\text{TeCl}_4(\text{CH}_2\text{NO}_2)_2$ having a light yellow colour. The formation of this product can be explained exactly as in reaction I but the solvate seems to be unstable.

Similarly arsenic (III) chloride and iron (III) chloride on refluxing with the solvent evolve hydrochloric acid gas and give solid compounds $\text{AsCl}(\text{CH}_2\text{NO}_2)_3 \cdot \text{CH}_2\text{NO}_2$ (grey)

and $\text{FeCl}_2 \cdot \text{CH}_2\text{NO}_2$ (dark brown). The reactions may be represented as follows:

where $\text{M} = \text{As}$ or Fe

In the case of $\text{FeCl}_2 \cdot \text{CH}_2\text{NO}_2$ the solvate probably is unstable and only the desolvated compound is obtained. Solvolytic reactions with Lewis acids resulting in the evolution of hydrochloric acid gas indicate the protonic nature of the solvent and confirm its autoionization as

Sodamide reacts with nitromethane in an exothermic reaction with the evolution of ammonia and the formation of sodium nitromethane:

Similarly its reaction with sodium hydride results in the evolution of hydrogen and formation of sodium nitromethane

which indicate the lability of one of the hydrogen atoms of methyl group and thus the protonic nature of the solvent.

Metathetical reactions: Metathetical reactions are well known in non-aqueous media and have been reported in a large number of solvents. Precipitation of the product may take place if the ions present in the solvent react to form a compound which has a higher lattice energy as compared to the energy of solvation. In aqueous systems such reactions are of great analytical importance. With a view to understand the role of the solvent, a few metathetical reactions have been carried out in this solvent.

On passing pure dry hydrogen sulphide gas through a solution of arsenic (III) chloride in nitromethane, a yellow precipitate of composition $\text{As}_2\text{S}_3 \cdot 3\text{CH}_2\text{NO}_2$ separates out. The reaction may be represented as:

Similar reactions of hydrogen sulphide with solutions of tin (IV) chloride and antimony(V) chloride in nitromethane result in the precipitation of $\text{SnS}_2 \cdot \text{CH}_2\text{NO}_2$ and Sb_2S_3 respectively. A similar action of hydrogen sulphide on the solutions of mercuric chloride, copper nitrate

cadmium nitrate results in the precipitation of their sulphides. Solutions of nitrates of zinc, cobalt and nickel in nitromethane react with dry hydrogen sulphide producing corresponding sulphides having similar colours as in aqueous system. The association of the solvent (Table I) with the precipitate indicates a situation similar to the aqueous system and that nitromethane helps in the reaction of ionic species already present in it.

TABLE I

Composition of compounds precipitated during metathetical reactions

Reactants	Product	Colour	Analysis			
			Sulphur%		Metal%	
			Found	Calculated	Found	Calculated
Arsenic chloride + Dry H ₂ S	As ₂ S ₃ .3CH ₃ NO ₂	Yellow	22.80	22.38	34.12	34.96
Tin (IV) chloride + Dry H ₂ S	SnS ₄ .CH ₃ NO ₂	Brown	26.12	26.34	48.35	48.56
Antimony (V) chloride + Dry H ₂ S	Sb ₂ S ₃	Orange	27.83	28.23	71.05	71.77
Mercury (II) nitrate + Dry H ₂ S	HgS	Black	13.90	13.73	85.31	86.27
Copper (II) sulphate + Dry H ₂ S	CuS. CH ₃ NO ₂	Black	20.13	20.44	40.23	40.57
Cadmium nitrate + Dry H ₂ S	CdS	Yellow	21.97	22.12	76.98	77.77
Lead nitrate + Dry H ₂ S	PbS	Black	13.14	13.39	86.71	86.67
Cobalt nitrate + Dry H ₂ S	CoS. CH ₃ NO ₂	Black	20.88	21.05	38.29	38.82
Nickel nitrate + Dry H ₂ S	NiS. CH ₃ NO ₂	Black	20.58	21.05	38.46	38.82
Manganese nitrate + Dry H ₂ S	Mn S. CH ₃ NO ₂	Light brown	21.61	21.62	36.87	37.16
Zinc nitrate + Dry H ₂ S	ZnS	White	33.12	33.33	74.12	74.71
Copper nitrate + H ₂ SO ₄	CuSO ₄ .CH ₃ NO ₂	White	14.10	14.51	27.90	28.80

Dry hydrochloric acid gas when passed through solutions of silver nitrate, lead nitrate and mercurous nitrate in nitromethane gives the precipitates of the respective chlorides.

Mixing of copper nitrate, solution in nitromethane with anhydrous sulphuric acid results in the formation of CuSO₄.CH₃NO₂.

All these reactions suggest that ions exist in nitromethane or this solvent provides similar facilities for the ions to react as water and assists in these reactions. These reactions confirm the autoionisation of the solvent as:

EXPERIMENTAL

Reagents were purified by methods already suggested(1)

General procedure for solvolysis: Anhydrous Lewis acid (5 g.) was added to pure and dry nitromethane (30 ml.) contained in a 100 ml. standard joint flask equipped with a water condenser and silica gel guard tube for exclusion of atmospheric moisture. The reaction mixture was refluxed for about 48 hours till there was no more evolution of hydrogen chloride gas. Nitromethane was replenished occasionally. The solid was filtered off under dry conditions, washed with dry carbon tetrachloride, dried and analysed to characterise the compound. In a few cases, the excess of nitromethane was distilled off and slurry so obtained was washed and dried in vacuum.

TABLE II

Solvolyzed Products

Lewis acid	Solvolyzed product	Colour	Melting point °C	Analysis			
				Required %		Found %	
				Metal	Chlorine	Metal	Chlorine
Antimony (V) chloride	$SbCl_5 \cdot 2CH_3NO_2 \cdot CH_3NO_2$	Light brown	Above 225	29.83	26.04	29.28	26.78
Titanium (IV) chloride	$TiCl_4 \cdot 2CH_3NO_2 \cdot 2CH_3NO_2$	Dark brown	Above 225	13.02	19.31	12.32	18.98
Tin (IV) chloride	$SnCl_4 \cdot CH_3NO_2 \cdot 2CH_3NO_2$	Light brown	Sublimates above 300	29.24	26.17	28.91	25.87
Aluminium (III) chloride	$AlCl_3 \cdot 2CH_3NO_2 \cdot CH_3NO_2$	Light brown	Above 225	11.09	14.58	10.93	14.80
Zirconium (IV) chloride	$ZrCl_4 \cdot 2CH_3NO_2 \cdot 2CH_3NO_2$	Light yellow	Above 225	22.52	17.57	22.34	17.23
Arsenic (III) chloride	$AsCl_3 \cdot 2CH_3NO_2 \cdot CH_3NO_2$	Light grey	above 225	23.79	12.14	25.35	12.06
Tellurium (IV) chloride	$TeCl_4 \cdot CH_3NO_2$	Light yellow	above 225	43.38	36.22	42.94	45.84
Iron (III) chloride	$FeCl_3 \cdot CH_3NO_2$	Dark brown	—	29.94	37.96	29.76	37.56

Metathetical reaction: The anhydrous compounds were dissolved in dry and pure nitromethane and then a steady stream of pure and dry hydrogen sulphide or hydrochloric acid gas was passed through it for a sufficiently long time. The precipitate so obtained was filtered under dry conditions, washed with dry carbon tetrachloride and dried in vacuum. It was analysed to characterise the compound.

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